

THE VALUE OF VOCABULARY FOR BEGINNERS

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ANOTATSIYA

So'z horijiy tilni o'rganishda muhim ahamiyatga ega va so'zlarda turli xil ma'nolar tashiydi. Agar o'quvchiga o'quv yili boshidan so'z yodlash ko'nikmasini shakillantirilsa, yil oxiriga kelib, har kunlik so'zlarni yodlab borgan bolalar qolganlarga qaraganda ikki baravar ko'p so'zlarni o'zlashtiradi. Maktablar boshlang'ich sinflarda bu natijani o'zgartirish uchun juda kam ish qilinadi, bu yerda lug'atga kam e'tibor beriladi. Agar so'z boyligi past bo'lgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari maktabda so'z boyligini oshirishga kam e'tibor bersalar, ular lug'at boyligi ustunroq bolalarga nisbatan orqada qolishda davom etadilar. Ko'p lug'atga ega bo'lgan o'quvchilar tomonidan matnlarni osonlik bilan tarjima qilinadi va tushunish oson bo'ladi, lekin lug'at boyligi kam bo'lganlar bundan mustasno.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari o'rgatilgan so'zlarni qanchalik yaxshi o'zlashtirilsa, keyingi sinflarda juda ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Xulosa qilib aytganda, ushbu maqola boshlang'ich sinflarda horijiy tilni o'rganishda lug'at boligi qanchalik muhim ekanligiga alohida urg'u beradi.

Words are important in learning a foreign language, and words carry different meanings. If a student is trained to memorize words from the beginning of the school year, by the end of the year, children who memorize words every day will learn twice as many words as the rest. little is done to change the outcome, little attention is paid to the vocabulary here. If low-vocabulary elementary

students receive little attention in school to improve their vocabulary, they will continue to lag behind children with higher vocabularies. Texts are easily translated and understood by students with large vocabularies, but those with low vocabularies are excluded.

The more elementary students master the words taught, the more useful they will be in later grades. In conclusion, this article emphasizes the importance of vocabulary in learning a foreign language in primary grades.

Слова играют важную роль в изучении иностранного языка, и слова имеют разные значения. Если ученика обучают запоминанию слов с начала учебного года, то к концу года дети, запоминающие слова каждый день, выучат в два раза больше слов, чем остальные. Мало делается для изменения результата, мало внимания уделяется здесь уделено словарному запасу. Если учащимся начальной школы с низким словарным запасом уделяется мало внимания в школе, чтобы улучшить свой словарный запас, они будут продолжать отставать от детей с более высоким словарным запасом. Тексты легко переводятся и понимаются учащимися с большим словарным запасом, но студенты с низким словарным запасом исключаются.

Чем лучше ученики начальной школы освоят преподаваемые слова, тем полезнее они будут в последующих классах. В заключение в данной статье подчеркивается важность словарного запаса при изучении иностранного языка в начальных классах.

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Abstract: Vocabulary is a powerful predictor and correlate of reading comprehension, and consequently of academic success. By the end of the grade two, children in the highest quartile know twice as many words as children in the lowest quartile. Schools have done little to change this outcome during the primary grades, where there is little attention to vocabulary. Unless primary grade children with low vocabularies have a chance to build vocabulary in school, they will continue to lag seriously behind more advantaged children. It is possible to identify high priority word meanings that are known by those with large vocabularies, but not known by those with small vocabularies. There is also good evidence that low-vocabulary children *can learn* needed words from classroom instruction. Teachers can assess how well taught vocabulary is learned by a class of primary grade children. In short, needed vocabulary can be taught and assessed in primary grades. It is time that this be done.

Introduction

There is much evidence that vocabulary levels are strongly correlated with reading comprehension (Biemiller, 1999; Chall, Jacobs, & Baldwin, 1990; Hart & Risley, 1995; Cunningham & Stanovich, 1997; Scarborough, 2001; Stahl & Nagy, 2006; Lescaux & Kieffer, 2010;). Chall et al, (1990) and Lescaux and Kieffer (2010) have shown that *vocabulary* is an increasingly important predictor of reading comprehension in higher grades. Thus, while vocabulary is a weak predictor of first grade reading achievement, it is a much stronger predictor of fourth grade reading achievement (Scarborough) and the main predictor by seventh or eighth grade (Lescaux & Kieffer, 2010). By the middle elementary grades, 95 percent of children can *read* more words than they *understand* (Biemiller, 2005). From grade three on, the main limiting factor for the majority of children, is vocabulary, not reading mechanics (decoding print into words).

The Relationship Between Vocabulary and Comprehension

In the primary grades, the range between children with smaller and bigger vocabularies is already large (Biemiller & Slonim, 2001; Biemiller, 2005). By the end of grade two, children in the lowest vocabulary quartile had acquired slightly more than 1.5 root words a day over 7 years for a total of about 4,000 root word meanings. In contrast, children in the highest quartile had acquired more than 3 root words a day for a total of about 8,000 root word meanings. Average vocabulary

increases from an estimated 3,500 root word meanings at the beginning of kindergarten to 6,000 at the end of second grade (Biemiller, 2005). These estimates are consistent with findings by Anglin (1993) and my own work, as well as studies of root word knowledge by beginning college students (Hazenbergh & Hulstijn, 1996; D'Anna, Zechmeister, & Hall, 1991; Goulden, Nation, and Read, 1990; Nation, 2001).

These large differences reflect many things: (a) levels of parental language support and encouragement, (b) other language sources (e.g., caregivers, day care, preschool, school, etc.), and (c) child constitutional differences in the ease of acquiring new words. However, after second grade, children in all vocabulary quartile groups may acquire new words at about the same rate, at least until grade six (Biemiller & Slonim, 2001). Therefore, it seems likely that much of the important vocabulary differences before Grade 3 reflect differences in experiences as well as constitutional factors.

Assessing Vocabulary in the Primary Grades: A Main Problem

A major barrier for including vocabulary in the primary curriculum is the difficulty of assessing vocabulary under classroom conditions. Testing children's vocabulary orally on a one-to-one basis is not difficult. The Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT) (Dunn & Dunn, 1997) and the Expressive Vocabulary Test (Williams, 1997) are well established. These and similar tests are predictive of later school achievement (Scarborough, 1998). However, none of these methods is feasible for classroom teachers, for such assessments typically take 10 to 15 minutes per student.

I believe that the inability to readily and directly assess vocabulary and vocabulary growth has been a major reason why vocabulary receives little attention in the primary grades. If vocabulary is to be taught in the primary grades, teachers will need to monitor children's acquisition of taught vocabulary. At present, the difficulty of assessing vocabulary with *preliterate* children (those who do not read at all or do not read well enough to be validly tested) is a real barrier for teachers. Practical methods for testing vocabulary with *groups* of preliterate children have not been available.

Conclusion

The research literature suggests that children can acquire an average of 10 words per week, assuming that around 25 words per week are taught. While this may not seem like a lot of words, vocabulary work on 40 weeks could add 400 root words to individual children’s vocabularies. Increasing vocabulary gains by 400 words a year would have a measurable effect on vocabulary size. If vocabulary instruction were sustained over three years, this would add about two thirds of the number of words needed to bring children from the lowest vocabulary quartile to average vocabulary levels, assuming that these children would continue to learn some words outside of school. This is true of children who are not reading fluently or widely. (Among older children, especially in middle and high school, there is some evidence that active inference may help with vocabulary learning.) During the primary years, new root words are learned mainly from explanations by others.

Other vocabulary methods could be used in addition. A “word of the day” could be added (preferably a word which will be used in the classroom). If children can be encouraged to ask about unfamiliar words—and parents can be persuaded to encourage such questions—more gains could be achieved. However, total gains greater than three words a day have yet to be seen (or attempted!).

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